

Integrating Enzyme Technologies into EU Policy Frameworks

Executive Summary

Enzyme technologies are revolutionising industries by providing sustainable, efficient, and non-toxic alternatives to conventional chemical-based processes. These innovations directly align with the European Union's (EU) safety goals under the European Green Deal¹, Circular Economy Action Plan², Safe and Sustainable by Design framework (SSbD)³, and the Clean Industrial Deal⁴. However, regulatory inconsistencies – particularly within chemical classifications – pose significant barriers to the widespread adoption of enzyme-based solutions.

This policy brief draws insights from the FNR-16 projects (EnXylaScope, FuturEnzyme, OXIPRO, and RadicalZ⁵) and extensive stakeholder and consumer surveys, highlights the economic and environmental benefits of enzyme technologies, identifies regulatory obstacles, and provides clear policy recommendations to position enzymes as catalysts for Europe's green and digital transition.

At the same time, it emphasises the urgent need to adapt EU regulations to fully harness enzyme technologies as sustainable alternatives to conventional chemicals.

Enzymes are proteins that act as biological catalysts and help speed up chemical reactions

Key Messages

Enzyme technologies are essential enablers of sustainable innovation

They reduce reliance on hazardous chemicals, lower energy and water use, and support the circular economy across sectors like textiles, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, and detergents.

Current EU regulations, especially under REACH, create barriers to enzyme adoption

Automatic classification of enzymes as hazardous substances (e.g. respiratory sensitisers) does not reflect their actual use-case safety, limiting innovation and market access.

Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) frameworks must better integrate sustainability

The SSbD process should consider not only safety but also environmental and socio-economic benefits of enzyme technologies, using balanced and holistic assessment approaches.

Policy support and regulatory streamlining are urgently needed

Fast-track approval pathways, harmonised regulations across member states, and reduced burdens for SMEs will help accelerate the uptake of enzyme-based innovations.

Investing in enzyme technologies will strengthen EU industrial competitiveness

Supporting enzyme innovation in biomanufacturing aligns with the EU Green Deal, Clean Industrial Deal, and Bioeconomy Strategy, positioning the EU as a global leader in sustainable industry.

The Role of Enzyme Technologies in Driving UN Sustainability Goals and the EU 2030 Agenda

Enzyme technologies serve as key enablers of Europe’s transition to a more sustainable and competitive bioeconomy. These biocatalysts enable processes that lead to energy savings, eliminate harsh, toxic chemicals, and reinforce circular economy principles. Findings from the FNR-16 projects demonstrate enhanced sustainability from enzyme applications across multiple consumer products. Despite these environmental and industrial advantages, the current regulatory framework for chemicals, particularly REACH⁶ classifications, present challenges to investment, innovation, and large-scale deployment of enzyme-assisted solutions.

Sector	Enzyme Application	Environmental & Economic Benefits	Alignment with EU Policies
Nutraceuticals	Enzymatic hydrolysis of fish byproducts into high-value protein supplements.	Reduces food waste and CO ² emissions. Increases resource efficiency. Supports circular bioeconomy principles.	Circular Economy Action Plan: Supports waste valorisation. Farm to Fork Strategy: Strengthens sustainable food systems. Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy: Supporting sustainable fisheries and aquaculture.
	Production of new compounds with prebiotic activity from secondary waste streams	Reduces food waste and CO ² emissions. Increases resource efficiency. Supports circular bioeconomy principles	Circular Economy Action Plan: Supports waste valorisation. Farm to Fork Strategy: Strengthens sustainable food systems.
Textiles	Enzymatic bleaching and fibre processing replace toxic oxidants.	Reduces water pollution and chemical waste. Lowers energy consumption. Enhances fabric durability.	Circular Economy Action Plan: Promotes sustainable textile production. Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability ⁷ compliance: Reduces hazardous chemical use.
	Textile production from yarn involves multiple chemical-intensive steps requiring hot water for removal, which can be significantly reduced using enzymes.	Reduced water and energy consumption while allowing the removal of chemicals (such as silicones, spinning oils, etc.) without damaging the surface, enhancing durability.	Circular Economy Action Plan: Promotes sustainable textile production. EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles: Lifecycle of textile products.
Personal care and cosmetics	Enzyme-based UV filters replace petro-derived alternatives in sunscreens.	Prevents marine pollution and coral bleaching. Reduces reliance on harmful petrochemicals. Enhances biodegradability.	EU Cosmetics Regulation: Ensures safe and sustainable ingredients. EU’s Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy: Protects marine ecosystems.
	Enzyme-synthesised aroma and antioxidant compounds replace oil-derived alternatives and can be labelled as “natural” ingredients.	Reduces reliance on harmful petrochemicals. Enhances biodegradability and boosts regional development (e.g. by localized raw material production and upgrading). Sustainable production by using renewable resources.	EU Cosmetics Regulation: Ensures safe and sustainable ingredients
	Enzyme-based transformation of high-molecular-weight hyaluronic acid into “Mini HA” hydrolysates.	Enzymes break down hyaluronic acid into Mini HA of a defined size, optimising its anti-aging properties in cosmetic formulations. Reduces energy consumption.	EU Green Deal and Circular Economy Action Plan: Reducing energy consumption. EU Cosmetic Regulation: Ensuring a more sustainable, eco-friendly ingredients.
Liquid Detergents	Enzymes enable cold-wash detergents with biodegradable surfactants.	Reduces energy use and CO ² emissions.- Minimises water pollution. Improves wastewater treatment efficiency.	Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability: Eliminates hazardous surfactants.
	Bio-based thickeners replace petrochemical-derived alternatives and are labelled as “natural” ingredients.	Use of secondary waste streams as feedstocks reduces reliance on harmful petrochemicals. Enhanced biodegradability of product and wastewater from their synthesis.	Circular Economy Action Plan: Waste and recycling Bioeconomy Action Plan.

Enzyme Technologies as Drivers of Sustainable Innovation across Key Sectors

A consumer survey revealed that while consumers value ecological solutions, they still prioritise product effectiveness, which can be effectively achieved through the application of enzyme technologies. Moreover, responses highlight enzyme technologies that enhance industrial efficiency, environmental protection, and product safety, reinforcing EU sustainability priorities.

Enzymes Align with Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) Principles

The SSbD framework provides a structured approach to developing chemicals, materials and processes that are both safe and sustainable. Survey results confirm that enzymes align with several of the **SSbD design guiding principles**:⁸

SSbD1: Improving material efficiency by enhancing resource valorisation through the direct use of crude effluents from which enzymes can generate value selectively.

SSbD2: By replacing chemical agents in detergent formulations, contributing to minimizing hazardous chemicals.

SSbD3: Minimising energy use in industrial processes by operating under milder conditions.

SSbD4: Use renewable resources as raw materials for enzymatic transformations.

SSbD5: Reducing hazardous emissions in marine and terrestrial ecosystems.

SSbD6: Reduce exposure to hazardous chemical feedstocks, reagents and solvents by enabling the use for milder, less toxic alternatives.

SSbD7: By producing molecules that degrade into harmless components that do not pose any risk to the environment/humans, and by designing recycling strategies for wastewater.

SSbD8: Enzymes enable sustainability across the entire product lifecycle, from raw material use and transformation into sustainable products to end-of-life recycling.

Of the five steps in the assessment phase, SSbD assessments prioritise hazard classification, safety, and health aspects (steps 1-3).

This emphasis may create a bias, potentially leading to the exclusion of enzyme innovations despite their environmental sustainability and socio-economic benefits (steps 4-5).

Recommendations:

Ensure SSbD methodologies balance safety with sustainability.

Practise SSbD in the upcoming Horizon Europe work programme and consult enzyme-experienced stakeholders to adapt and improve methodologies as experience and knowledge become available.

Introduce standardised social and economic assessments to ensure a holistic sustainability evaluation.

Consider a matrix-based structure with multi-harmonised criteria decision analysis rather than the hierarchical approach currently undertaken.

Regulatory Barriers Under REACH Must Be Addressed

Survey findings highlight industry-wide concerns over the current automatic classification of enzymes as respiratory sensitisers (Category 1) under REACH, regardless of use case or exposure risk. This blanket classification of enzymes as 'substances of concern'⁹ threatens to limit market access for safe and beneficial enzyme-based products.

Recommendations:

Exempt enzymes from Category 1 Respiratory Sensitisers when used in low-risk, encapsulated, or controlled applications.

Ensure that historical safe use is considered in risk assessments.

Apply a case-by-case risk assessment instead of one-size-fits-all hazard classifications to ensure balanced regulation.

Ensure case-by-case optimisation of enzyme formulations by prioritising liquid, granulated, or immobilised advanced forms over fine powders, following SSbD principles.

Enzyme Technologies Support the European Green Deal, Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Strategies

Enzymes technologies are crucial enablers of the European Green Deal, Circular Economy and Bioeconomy strategies by reducing chemical use and waste, valorising industrial by-products and producing new molecules, and improving resource efficiency.

The FNR-16 projects demonstrate enzyme applications that directly support:

European Green Deal: The enzymatic production of advanced ingredients in consumer products enables the reduction of wastewater and energy consumption during both production and use phases, leading to lower Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions.

Farm to Fork Strategy: Enzymatic processes extract bioactives from fish waste and forestry by-products, reducing food system losses and improving nutraceutical production.

Zero Pollution Action Plan: Enzymatic detergents, containing less chemicals and requiring a lower dosage per wash, reduce water contamination and enable milder, less environmentally harmful wastewater treatments.

Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability: Boosting the innovation capacity for the production of safe and sustainable bioactive molecules. The enzyme-based production of advanced ingredients, especially those that cannot be obtained through conventional methods, enables high-functional cosmetic formulations (Cosmetic Strategy).

Industrial Strategy: Boosting methodologies that enable the transition to a green and digital economy.

Textile Strategy: Enzyme-based bleaching and cleaning eliminate or facilitate the removal of toxic chemicals from yarn while reducing water and energy consumption. Additionally, enzyme-based solutions support the recycling of textiles, making the process more sustainable.

Recommendations:

Integrate enzyme innovation at all TRLs into sustainable EU Bioeconomy and Circular Economy funding programs.

Facilitate regulatory approvals for enzyme-driven valorisation, renewable and recycling technologies.

Enhancing European Competitiveness in Biomanufacturing

The Clean Industrial Deal and EU Industrial Strategy 2030 prioritize sustainable manufacturing and technological leadership. Enzyme technologies can drive the shift towards biomanufacturing, reducing the EU's reliance on fossil-based chemical processes and its dependence on imports.

Recommendations:

Provide financial incentives for enzyme-based biomanufacturing under new funding calls.

Streamline regulatory pathways to accelerate enzyme commercialisation.

Support the establishment of EU-wide enzyme innovation hubs and clusters to foster research collaboration.

Policy Recommendations for Enzyme Integration

To align enzyme technologies with the EU's sustainability and industrial strategies, policymakers should consider the following actions:

Update REACH to reflect enzyme-specific properties.

Establish dedicated assessment criteria that consider enzyme biodegradability and low toxicity.

Differentiate (biochemical) enzymes from conventional chemical substances in classification and risk evaluation.

Harmonise enzyme regulations across EU member states.

Encourage mutual recognition of enzyme safety assessments across regulatory bodies.

Streamline approval processes for sustainable biotechnologies.

Introduce fast-track approval pathways for enzyme innovations that meet EU sustainability objectives.

Reduce administrative burdens for SMEs and start-ups bringing enzyme-based solutions to market.

Promote enzyme awareness and market uptake.

Develop public awareness campaigns on the safety and benefits of enzymes and enzyme-based products.

Support industrial transition programs to encourage private-sector adoption of enzyme technologies.

By implementing these policy reforms, the EU can unlock the full potential of enzyme technologies, driving innovation while achieving its ambitious climate and industrial objectives.

Conclusion

Aligned with past evidence, the FNR-16 projects highlight the transformative potential of enzyme technologies in achieving Europe's sustainability and industrial goals. However, to fully leverage these benefits, policy measures are urgently needed to ensure that enzymes are not disproportionately restricted under existing regulatory frameworks.

By implementing risk-balanced, science-driven regulations and incentivising enzyme innovation, the EU can lead the global shift towards sustainable industrial biotechnology while enhancing economic competitiveness.

Enzyme technologies offer a win-win solution for Europe's environmental and economic goals by reducing industrial carbon footprints, improving efficiency, and fostering sustainable manufacturing. However, to fully leverage their potential, EU policymakers must address regulatory barriers that hinder their adoption. By modernising regulations, harmonising policies, and supporting market integration, enzymes can become central drivers of Europe's green and circular economy.

This policy brief urges the European Commission, national governments, and industry leaders to take decisive action in integrating enzyme technologies within the EU policy framework, ensuring their role in shaping the sustainable industries of tomorrow.

1. <https://ec.europa.eu/green-deal>

2. <https://ec.europa.eu/circular-economy-action-plan>

3. <https://ec.europa.eu/ssbd-framework>

4. https://commission.europa.eu/topics/en-competitiveness/clean-industrial-deal_en

5. <https://www.enxylascope.eu/>; <https://www.futureenzyme.eu/>; <https://www.oxipro.eu/>; <https://radicalz.eu/>

6. <https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach>

7. <https://echa.europa.eu/hot-topics/chemicals-strategy-for-sustainability>

8. https://www.parc-ssbd.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/JRC131878_01.pdf; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsc.2023.100876>

9. https://www.europabio.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/2022_08_PP_AMFEP-EuropaBio-Position-on-Taxonomy.pdf

10. <https://www.enzymetechnicalassociation.org/enzymes/safe-handling-enzymes/#:~:text=In%20fact%2C%20rennet%20has%20been,%2C%20starch%2C%20and%20baking%20industries;>

<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/7464>; <https://amfep.org/about-enzymes/safety/consumers-safety/>.

European Cluster - Enzymes for Greener Products

EnXylaScope

Unleashing xylan's potential with enzymes to make it a key ingredient for a scope of bio-based consumer products

<https://www.enxylascope.eu/>

FuturEnzyme

Developing future technologies for low-cost enzymes for more sustainable and environmentally friendly consumer products

<https://www.futureenzyme.eu/>

OXIPRO

Harnessing the power of novel oxidoreductases - diversifying enzymes for environment friendly consumer products

<https://www.oxipro.eu/>

RadicalZ

Developing novel tools for faster enzyme discovery and engineering to support the creation of greener products

<https://radicalz.eu/>

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